

Metal Complexes of N-Salicylidene 5-Bromoanthranilic acid (I)

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A tridentate ligand has been synthesised by condensing 5-bromoanthranilic acid and salicylaldehyde which forms solid complexes with Fe (II) Co(II), and Ni (II). The stoichiometry and structure of these complexes and their pyridino derivatives have been studied and tetrahedral structure assigned to them.

ANTHRANILIC acid combines with divalent metal ions through carboxyl and amino groups to form metal chelates. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to prepare a tridentate ligand by condensing 5-bromoanthranilic acid and salicylaldehyde. The resulting product, N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilic acid was found to be a tridentate ligand containing a carboxylic, a phenolic and an imino group. With metals like Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) this ligand forms solid complexes. The stoichiometry and structure of these complexes have been investigated and analytical and magnetic susceptibility studies on N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilates of Fe(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Preparation of N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid: 5-Bromoanthranilic acid was prepared by

Nickel acetate (3.5 g) in solution was added to ethanolic solution of freshly distilled salicylaldehyde (2.5 g). To this an ethanolic solution of 5-bromoanthranilic acid (4.3 g) was added gradually with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for about 2 hrs on a water bath. It was then filtered and the filtrate concentrated. On cooling, a crop of light green crystals of N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilic acid nickel was obtained. Heating pure N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilic acid nickel (0.8g) with pyridine (10 ml) on steam bath and concentration of the solution in vacuum gave green crystals of the pyridino-metal complex.

Stoichiometry and Structure

I. Elemental Analysis: The chief constituents of the complexes, the metal, nitrogen and bromine in addition to water of coordination, were determined by standard methods^{2,3}. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Metal Complex	%Water		%Nitrogen		%Bromine		%Metal	
	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found
Fe(C ₁₄ H ₈ BrNO ₃)H ₂ O	4.595	4.50	3.574	3.51	20.39	20.30	14.26	14.18
Co(C ₁₄ H ₈ BrNO ₃)H ₂ O	4.560	4.51	3.546	3.45	20.24	20.19	14.93	14.87
Ni(C ₁₄ H ₈ BrNO ₃)H ₂ O	4.561	4.49	3.547	3.46	20.24	20.26	14.88	14.83

bromination of anthranilic acid dissolved in glacial acetic acid (i). To the alcoholic solution of 5-bromoanthranilic acid (2.1 g) was added distilled salicylaldehyde (1.2 g) in alcohol with constant stirring. A yellow crystalline mass was formed within five minutes. The mixture was refluxed for half an hour and then concentrated on a water bath. On cooling fine shining crystals of the Schiff's base were obtained which were further purified by recrystallisation.

Analysis: Analysis of the Schiff's base gave the following results:

Calculated for	Br	C	H	N	Percent
(C ₁₄ H ₁₀ BrNO ₃)	24.98	52.52	3.12	4.37	"
Found	24.91	52.30	3.20	4.27	"

Following method was used for the preparation of the nickel complex. Complexes of Fe(II) and Co(II) were also prepared in the same way.

II. Molecular Weight Determination: Molecular weight of the complexes was determined with a semimicro ebulliometer (Gallenkemp). For the hydrated metal complexes pyridine was used as solvent and while calculating the molecular weight a correction was applied as the water molecule is replaced by pyridine in the complex.

TABLE 2

Metal complex	Molecular weight Calcd	weight Found
<i>Hydrated metal complex</i>		
Fe(C ₁₄ H ₈ BrNO ₃)H ₂ O	394.6	402
Co(C ₁₄ H ₈ BrNO ₃)H ₂ O	394.6	406
Ni(C ₁₄ H ₈ BrNO ₃)H ₂ O	394.8	409
<i>Pyridino-metal complex</i>		
Fe(C ₁₄ H ₇ BrNO ₃)(C ₅ H ₅ N)	455.6	469
Co(C ₁₄ H ₇ BrNO ₃)(C ₅ H ₅ N)	455.6	462
Ni(C ₁₄ H ₇ BrNO ₃)(C ₅ H ₅ N)	455.8	472

III. Magnetic Susceptibility Measurements : Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with Gouy apparatus at 300°K using nickel chloride as the standard reference and making diamagnetic correction for the ligand and one molecule of water coordinated with the metal ion in the complex. The magnetic moments of the complexes and proposed bond type are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Metal complex	Magnetic moment B. M.	No. of unpaired electrons	Proposed bond type
<i>Hydrated complex</i>			
Fe(II) complex	5.22	4	sp ³
Co(II) complex	4.59	3	sp ³
Ni(II) complex	3.76	2	sp ³
<i>Pyridino complex</i>			
Fe(II) complex	5.20	4	sp ³
Co(II) complex	4.56	3	sp ³
Ni(II) complex	3.74	2	sp ³

Discussion

N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilato iron (II) with 5.2 B.M. may be assigned tetrahedral structure involving sp³ hybridisation. N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilato cobalt (II) and its pyridine derivative having magnetic moment 4.59 and 4.56 respectively may be assigned a tetrahedral structure.

Magnetic moments of N-salicylidene-5-bromoanthranilato nickel (II) and the pyridine derivative are 3.76 and 3.4 respectively at 300°K. These spin complexes may, therefore, be assigned tetrahedral structure.

The molecular weights indicate that the hydrated as well as the pyridino-metal complexes exist as monomers in solid state and there is 1:1 metal to ligand ratio. In the pyridino complexes the coordination position occupied by water is taken up by pyridine. The following structure is proposed for the N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilates of Fe(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) and their pyridine derivative, where M=Fe, Co or Ni and L=H₂O or C₅H₅N.

References

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